

Example of semi-structured interviewing for the Open Research Europe article “Automated news in practice”: questionnaire developed to interview an executive at *The Washington Post*.

- Could you please tell me a bit about yourself?
- I’ve been following what the Post has been doing with [the automated journalism software] Heliograf (Rio Olympics, 2016 elections), then I saw the Computational Journalism Lab for this year’s elections. Could you please give me an overview of automated text generation projects at the Post?
- Why going for an in-house solution rather than outsourcing automated news to an external NLG provider or using a third party tool?
- How is editorial staff involved in creating automated news at the Post?
- When writing templates, how do they balance predicting elements of the story in advance with the uncertainty of news?
- How do you make sure data sources selected for automated news are diverse enough?
- What about important aspects of the story that cannot be automated?
- What safeguards do you have to prevent unwarranted content from creeping into the final copy?
- How do you make sure to embed the Post’s journalistic standards and practices into the conception of automated news?
- How did work routines/media coverage change at the Post after the implementation of automated news?

- What unforeseen situation did you run into while using automated news to cover this year's election?